

CZU data platform: Initial Study

Michal Stočes

*Department of Information
Technologies*
Czech University of Life Sciences
Prague
Prague, Czech Republic
stoces@pef.czu.cz

Vojtěch Novák

*Department of Information
Technologies*
Czech University of Life Sciences
Prague
Prague, Czech Republic
novakvojtech@pef.czu.cz

Petr Cihelka

*Department of Information
Technologies*
Czech University of Life Sciences
Prague
Prague, Czech Republic
cihelka@rektorat.czu.cz

Miloš Ulman

*Department of Information
Technologies*
Czech University of Life Sciences
Prague
Prague, Czech Republic
ulman@pef.czu.cz

Martin Havránek

*Department of Information
Technologies*
Czech University of Life Sciences
Prague
Prague, Czech Republic
havranek@pef.czu.cz

Lukáš Kovář

*Department of Information
Technologies*
Czech University of Life Sciences
Prague
Prague, Czech Republic
kovarlukas@pef.czu.cz

Jiří Vaněk

*Department of Information
Technologies*
Czech University of Life Sciences
Prague
Prague, Czech Republic
vanek@pef.czu.cz

Pavel Simek

*Department of Information
Technologies*
Czech University of Life Sciences
Prague
Prague, Czech Republic
simek@pef.czu.cz

Abstract— The paper presents the user needs and architecture design of the Data Platform CZU (Czech University of Life Sciences Prague). It is a unified repository for heterogeneous scientific research data from the field of Life Sciences. The article deals with the issue of the current state of data storage, user needs of the new and the design of individual parts of the unified data storage. The data warehouse is currently in pilot operation. Currently, supported data types are files, time series, tabular data with relations, Geospatial data, images and videos.

Keywords— data, data platform, data warehouse, life sciences, FAIR data principles, data collection, data catalogue, API

I. INTRODUCTION

With the advent of new technologies, sharing data worldwide through the internet has become easily achievable and cost-effective. The initiative of Open Data [6] [4] has propelled the sharing of data in machine-readable formats, primarily focusing on the publication of public sector data. Open Science is currently a prevailing trend, stemming from the idea popularised by Robert King Merton in the early 1940s that scientific research should be freely accessible to all [3]. The notion behind Open Science is that research-generated data should be openly shared for the common good. This concept has the potential to make the scientific process more transparent, inclusive, and democratic, and it is increasingly recognised as a critical accelerator for achieving sustainable development goals and addressing gaps in science, technology, and innovation while upholding the human right to science [8].

Accurate metadata description and standardisation are crucial to enhance the reusability of scientific data. The FAIR (Findable Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)+ principles initiative addresses this concern. In 2016, "The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship

was published in the Scientific Data Journal [9]. The authors aimed to provide guidelines for improving the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of digital assets. The principles emphasise machine-actionability, as computational systems play an increasingly significant role in data manipulation due to the growing volume, complexity, and speed of data creation. The methodological framework presented in the publication outlines how to publish data and is based on fifteen principles organised into four groups: Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability. The FAIR principles are also embraced by research funding providers such as Horizon Europe, The Technology Agency of the Czech Republic, and others [5].

Data are stored and further provided using so-called data repositories. The current trend is to connect national, thematic and other repositories using metadata catalogs so that the data can be traced from one place [7]. The issue of data sharing and the creation of a repository at the national level or at the level of scientific societies is one of the research and innovation strategies of the European Commission. This strategy is presented under the term European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) [1]. In the Czech Republic, the project deals with this issue: Project to create a modernized national large research e-infrastructure e-INFRA CZ, which is formed by a consortium of organizations CESNET, CERIT-SC and IT4Innovations.

The current trend in research data is to increase its reusability. Closely related to this are the concept of Open Science and a methodological set of principles, referred to as the FAIR principles, which define how to deal with scientific data so that it can be further shared and reused by the relevant scientific communities. At the same time, field-oriented data models are being developed, which define how to efficiently store and share the data of a given scientific field, e.g. BrAPI

(Breeding API), MIAPPE (Minimum Information About Plant Phenotyping Experiments).

The Breeding API project is an effort to enable interoperability among plant breeding databases. BrAPI is a standardised RESTful web service API specification for communicating plant breeding data. This community-driven standard is free to be used by anyone interested in plant breeding data management.

MIAPPE, as an open and community-driven initiative, establishes a standardised framework for consolidating data from plant phenotyping experiments. It furnishes a comprehensive specification comprising a checklist and a structured data model to ensure thorough documentation of these experiments. These specifications have been integrated into various tools, databases, and file formats, enabling seamless validation, storage, and dissemination of MIAPPE-compliant data.

A recent survey by [1] revealed that a significant proportion (46%) of biologists need to gain the knowledge to organise data for its extended usability effectively.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The article is thematically focused on the issue of data storage - repositories. The paper's main goal is to present the newly emerging data repository of the Czech University of Life Sciences called the Data Platform of the Czech University of Life Sciences. Subgoals include analysing the current status of cargo with scientific data. Analyse current trends and user requirements for data storage. Design the architecture and essential functions of the new repository.

In the first phase, an extensive analysis of the current state of handling data from research results will be carried out, and their requirements for data storage will also be determined. This will be done based on guided interviews with members of the research groups. The obtained requirements were confronted with the current state of the issue. From these results, user needs for data storage were formulated. And defined pilot data sets to integrate into the platform. Based on these requirements, a data flow model in the platform was designed. This model has been validated with users.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Current state:

Interviews with members of the scientific teams revealed that each group stores data in a different way. The differences are significant, from saving on a USB flash drive to cloud drives to sophisticated systems.

The following main issues were identified:

- No or insufficient backup.
- Poor data description, and lengthy data retrieval.
- Poor data protection.
- Difficulty sharing data with other scientific teams.

B. User needs:

- Improving data organisation – metadata, access control.
- Ability to easily share data with other communities, FAIR data principles.

- Automated data collection processes, for example, sensory data from the Internet of Things.
- Management of data sources, and settings for automated downloads and scraping data.
- Guaranteeing data persistence - scientists do not want to solve the backup problem.
- Automated and secured backup.
- Direct access to data using specialised software tools via API (RESTful API) (e.g. R language or python).
- All data is in one place – to access the terabytes of data via one single endpoint.
- Ontology field usage and API

C. Pilots driven development

It was decided to develop a pilot version of the application based on pilots from different disciplines and different data. The following data types were selected TABLE I.

The pilot-driven development approach in software solutions offers a strategic edge by allowing stakeholders to conduct live tests and validations in real-world settings before full-scale implementation. This method facilitates early user involvement, leading to more tailored and user-friendly solutions, ultimately reducing the likelihood of expensive post-deployment modifications.

TABLE I. FIRST PILOTS AND DATA FORMATS

Type of data	Pilot name
Files (CSV, ...)	Biological processes modelling - APSIM
Time lines / JSON	IoT sensors networks
Video recordings	Birds Online
Structured data / field of study interface	Data from the area of plant phenotyping (BrAPI)

Data categories:

The data categories listed below are determined based on the possibilities of data storage with current database technologies. And that both local implementation and possibly the cloud. On the basis of pre-prepared templates, the input API layer decides on the selection of a suitable data storage for the respective data types. Appropriate templates must be developed for new data types. Relational (like SQL base), Document stores (NoSQL databases), Time Series (InfluxDB), Key-value Stores, Search Engines

Structured data:

- Text documents in CSV, XML, JSON, YAML etc.
- Time series data and tabular database data.

Data of binary-specific formats

- Multimedia files: video, photo, audio.
- Special data files of proprietary measurement devices. mostly, for example, raw data.

Geospatial data (GIS data)

- Satellite, aerial, and radar images.
- Geographically located raster and vector data.
- Data collected by drones.

A specific category of data is metadata, which is related to all the above file types and continuously records the life cycle of the data. The CMDB system is used to record metadata.

Metadata is divided according to the nature of creation and meaning into:

- Basic/System - They are defined by the physical existence of the data source, serve to configure transmission paths and define the basic identity of the data record)
- Installation/experimental - They arise immediately after the installation of a sensory device, or during an ongoing experiment. They carry information about the used measuring device, the measurement methods and conditions of measurement, the location and time of data acquisition and the units of the measured quantity. It is also related to specific persons responsible for data acquisition and potential technological solution suppliers.
- Portable - They are created by the transfer of data between individual systems. For example, in the case of wireless transmissions, these are the radio parameters of the transmission, in the case of data transmission via web APIs, this is the identity of the provider, etc.
- Users - They can include any custom objects and notes to improve data reuse and data management.
- Analytical metadata is created during data processing, particularly the analytical methods used, the author of the new version of the data set, etc.
- Catalogue/accessibility- It is used to configure the provision of data sets, in particular the authorisation matrix, the method of storage and backup, etc.

D. Data Flows and Data Platform Design

Main defined user sections Fig. 1

- Web portal – user gateway to the data platform, access to data and metadata.
- Data catalogue – user interface for browsing and searching datasets. The catalogue contains an interface to machine browsing of the catalogue and sharing of information from the catalogue.
- Data input interface (API) - Management portal Tool for managing external data sources (IoT devices, ...) Connectivity methodology (technologies and standards supported – LoRaWAN (Long Range Wide Area Network), 5G, ...), Security methodology.

Fig. 1. User parts and data flow

A significant trend of sharing results worldwide among scientific teams. A pilot has been implemented within the data management platform for the area of plant phenotyping, where the world industry standard for the description of plant characteristics is used - BrAPI (communication) + MIAPE (ontology, dictionaries). Fig. 2 shows the user parts and data flows of the BrAPI implementation into the data platform. The import of data from phenotyping machines and data sharing with other scientific communities are also considered here.

Ready for further implementation, e.g. hydrology, economics.

Fig. 2. User parts and data flow BrAPI implementation to Data Platform

E. Data Source and Management Portal (IoT)

The management portal serves as a critical tool for administering and configuring connectors that establish connections with various data sources. These connectors enable the automatic acquisition of data from the respective sources. To streamline this process and enhance efficiency, templates are proposed, which will serve as predefined structures representing specific categories or classes of data sources. Part of the management portal deals with the special case of data sources - IoT sensors. The IoT portal enables and monitors the device's status, such as battery status, signal quality, date of last sensor calibration, and the like. The management portal also includes a Configuration Management Database (CMDB).

In an age of escalating cyber threats, combining robust cybersecurity with an advanced data platform is crucial for safeguarding information. Encryption and multi-factor authentication demonstrate a commitment to defence. Regular assessments and proactive monitoring show a readiness to identify and mitigate risks. Standardised compliance

frameworks ensure privacy and regulatory adherence. Secure coding practices minimise vulnerabilities. User education fosters a culture of cybersecurity awareness. This integrated approach sets a standard for secure data management in a rapidly evolving digital landscape.

IV. CONCLUSION

The platform aims to achieve complete universality in handling data, which is made possible through the modular design of the entire solution. This modularity allows for the selection of different storage methods based on specific data categories. A well-defined architecture for data storage has been established, particularly addressing the challenges of Big Data. Big Data refers to extensive datasets generated by internet users, requiring specialised storage, comprehension, and utilisation of tools and methods. An example of the use of big data tools can be, for example, a large study dealing with the analysis of available data from large agricultural enterprises. For such studies, analyses are performed on large datasets over data in various formats and quantities. An example is the project "Precision Agriculture and Digitization in the Czech Republic" no: QK23020058 supported by the National Agricultural Research Agency (NAZV). The data platform adopts a categorisation approach, where data is organised into distinct categories and progressively transformed based on desired output properties. A metadata structure is employed and integrated with the data catalogue to ensure the data's lifecycle and facilitate efficient management.

A. Data Flows and Data Platform Design

- Data is stored "forever". Unused data is long-term stored in an archive or on low-cost storage.
- There is almost no limitation to data size and format.
- Immutability of data - the way the data is stored, the way the data is retrieved/provided.
- Implement an alerting system for monitoring the functionality and relevance of the data source. Here it is mainly about the post-loaded data, e.g. from sensors.
- Metadata description (basic, related to the field of study, related to FAIR data sharing principles). and other metadata to connect the data platform with other international scientific groups and institutions.
- Unique identification - selected datasets – DOI (Digital Object Identifier).
- Data is stored in two repositories + tape backup, and cloud storage in the EU, for reasons of the GDPR (The General Data Protection Regulation) regulation.
- Creating the structure and roles of administrators, and managers: data manager, data steward, data owner, and user.
- Documents and support in the creation of a Data Management Plan (DMP) for the needs and support of projects. DMP is a standard and a necessity in project management.
- Access data monitoring -to enhance cybersecurity, it is crucial to implement robust data monitoring

practices, which involve continuous surveillance and analysis of network activities to identify and address potential threats promptly. The individual collections will be further recorded on tapes.

- Significant emphasis is placed on fortifying data security across the entirety of the solution, with particular attention paid to bolstering cyber security measures. This encompasses implementing robust protocols, encryption mechanisms, access controls, and intrusion detection systems to safeguard sensitive data from unauthorised access, breaches, and malicious activities.

The data is accessible based on the rules determined by the owner - internal, open data, according to the conditions (e.g. monetisation).

The following steps are implemented in the platform so that it is possible to implement the FAIR principles:

Establish Clear Metadata Standards: Implement FAIR data principles in your data platform by ensuring that all datasets have standardised and comprehensive metadata, including information on provenance, licensing, and usage restrictions. This enables easy discovery and understanding of the data's context and usage.

Enable Robust Data Linking and Integration: Create a framework within your data platform that allows for seamless linking and integration of diverse datasets. This promotes interoperability and facilitates the combination of data from different sources, supporting the "Findable" and "Accessible" aspects of FAIR principles.

Implement Persistent Identifiers (PIDs): Ensure that each dataset in your platform is assigned a unique and persistent identifier, such as a Digital Object Identifier (DOI). This practice enhances data traceability and citability, aligning with the "Identifiable" and "Reusable" components of FAIR data principles.

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